

DETERMINANTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE USING THE TALENT MANAGEMENT CONSTRUCTS- A MEDIATING ROLE OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

“Talent Management” is a one stop single solution for the problems related to the attraction and retention of the qualified employees. (Ejovwokeoghene et al., 2018). Attracting and retaining the best talent would be most complex process in the next decade. Rather than a process talent management is a strategy which will retain the best talents and increases the organizational performance. (Sivathanu & Pillai, 2020). There is a positive relationship, job satisfaction and the performance of the employees. (Wickramaratchi & Perera, 2020). This study aims to study the talent management practices and its effect on the positive performance of the organization using a structured questionnaire. The responses were collected from 183 respondents and the analysis were done through SPSS 25.0 using descriptive statistics, correlation, multiple regression tools. The results of the study proves that talent management practices is having an effect on the productive performance of the organization. Further to the hypothesis, a structural equation modeling is framed to prove that, employee engagement mediates the relationship between the TM practices and the organizational performance.

Keywords: Talent Management ; Talent Retention ; Career Management ; Training and Development ; Onboarding ; Human Resource Management.

Introduction:

Talent is something that one is born with and in due course of time identifies it and tries to hone it to improve his/her life eventually. Singing, Dancing, Painting and other such calibers are referred as talents. Unlike skills they cannot be learned. Talent is innate.

However in HR and workplace register talent refers to people who possess the adequate skill to perform better in the organization. Both the Corporate and Industries are much concerned about this talent to march forward in their business in this competitive era. In India, it is found that 25 percent difference in attrition

rate converts into a million-dollar organizational expenditure to replace the employees for every 50 positions in the firm states Dhanabhakya, , & Kokilambal (2014). Therefore it is evident that there is a demand of talent and hence it needs management at all levels.

Talent management has to start from the interview process to check if the employee is a right fit to the organization till employee separation where the employee parts the organization. The efforts taken towards the maintenance of talents would reap the benefits required to run the organisations meeting the goals set. As majority of the workforce align their talent to the goals of the organisation in the process of training and talent management practises. It is suggested therefore that organisations must have meaningful descriptions of the capabilities (skills, behaviours, abilities and knowledge) required of that particular organisation.

Similarly organisations must be able to relate the talents and skills to a role in the workplace such as a job position, project or leadership. Also talent management practises must create a comprehensive profile of people associated with the organisation. Moreover the certified training that is offered to the employee should boost their effectiveness and efficiency claims Tiwari & Shrivastava (2013).

Review of literature:

Baharin, & Hanafi (2018) considers employees as heart as soul of a company. According to them regardless of what the size of the company is, there must be quality set of strategies to harness the talents that the workforce of the organisation relies on for their productivity. In the context of hospitality sector the study proves that it is very essential for the organisation to identify high performers, their knowledge gaps and then devise initiatives to enhance their capabilities to align them to the company's. It is strongly believed that especially in the hospitality sector when the learning environment is built in an organisation then the value of the organisation is automatically increased. Identifying the right talent management practises that would lead to employee performance and retention would be the rewarding to both the growth of the employee and the organisation in general.

Hafez et al. (2017) studied a public university to understand the talent management practises and its effect. The job satisfaction level of 105 administrative staff of the public university were analysed to derive the results of the research. The success of any organisation largely depends on the performance of the employees, and an educational institution is no different from any organisation with employees exhibiting their potentials at different roles. The scholars and academicians do have to consider the cultural context while designing the talent management strategies to suit the requirement of the organisational set up. The purpose of the talent management must ultimately make the employee feel that their job brings them satisfaction. Job satisfaction is not an independent factor it largely depends on various factors and those need to be addressed while framing strategies for talent management practises. Especially in an educational organisation the employees vary based on their educational qualification, culture and gender. So when these demographic factors are also considered largely for implementation of appropriate practise then the desired outcome of the talent management initiative would be attained.

Alias et al. (2016) conducted a similar research in IT field. The constant availability of large, talented and experienced pool of employees in the IT industry make it all the more necessary to cater the suitable talent management practices to give rewarding results. Both employee engagement and retention practices were equally given importance and attention. Managerial support, suitable role attribution, career development initiatives, rewards and recognitions were analysed to identify the impact. It was found that there was a considerable effect of talent management practises on employee performance and retention. The further study on how these variables co relate with each other could be undertaken to understand the impact of each variable on each other for further classification of practices and appropriate approach to the talent management as a whole.

Narayanan (2016) declares that talent management practises are the only means for the retention of talented pool of employees in any organisation. With the theoretical framework, the researcher puts forth that job embeddedness is the tool to measure the rate of influence of the talent management practices on the retention rate of the employee. Similarly the various factor of job embeddedness is studied to understand the influence of the talent management practises. This study provides the required insight to HR practitioners to segment their focus on the talent management practises strategies that would be

proportionate to the factors that lead to the retention of the employee. The categorization of proper fit, link and sacrifice associated with job embeddedness would make sense to understand the effect of the initiatives taken in this regard.

Cappelli(2008)in a review article for Harvard had discussed the talent management required for the twentieth first century organisational setup.Since many failures were witnessed in the earlier times in terms of poor employee retention and wastage of costly training given at the time of recruitment, there existed confusion about where and on whom to invest time and resource to reap the desired benefits of the training and development practices. First it was suggested to adapt to the uncertainty of the demand of talent that existed. The return on investment in developing the employees was crucial. Therefore a balance between the employees – employer interest needs to be established first. The talent problem largely exists in all the sectors of business. The conflicting expectations of the industry are not rightly met by the employers, as they want the skills they want in the cost they can afford, whereas employees seek for career advancements and control over their growth. Striking a balance between these would be the issue that the modern HR practitioners have to address first.

Vural et al. (2012)suggest that it is not advisable to spend time in search for right talent and try to manage them. Rather to make performance sustainable of the existing employees it is essential for the organisation to provide commitment, Therefore the paper attempts to study the effect of employee engagement practices on the employee commitment. IT has been evident that companies have not been successful enough in identifying, developing and retaining the right talent for a long term, which proves very costly for the organisation on a longer run. As the organisation follows the structure of talent measurement suggested by the market, it is quite likely that they fail to narrow their suitable find. And this quite evident in the results of the current study, which show that the organisation employ the talent management strategies as a sub process of the basic education, performance and recruitment process, however the purpose of such initiatives are directed towards employee, their growth and commitment.

Amiri(2015) defines talent management as a function that the organisation undertakes for creation, integration and application of talent. If the talent management practices are effective the employees in turn feel the sense of belonging and exhibit strong engagement in the organisation. Though the function is solely the HR department concern but the practices must be implemented in almost all the areas and levels of the organisation.

Research Methodology

The structure questionnaire is constructed based on six constructs shown in the hypothesized model. The questionnaire is constructed based on the earlier model proposed by Al Aina&Atan (2020). The questionnaire were administered to 173 middle level employees of the IT and ITES Sector in the Chennai city to test the effect on talent management practices on the organizational performance. The questionnaire consists of 24 variables which is as follows. Talent Acquisition and On boarding(5) ,Talent Retention (5),Career Management(3),Employee Engagement (4),Talent Philosophy (3),Organizational Performance (4)Based on simple random sampling, people are chosen from various departments for obtaining the random sampling. The responses were statistically analysed using Descriptive statistics, Correlation, Multiple regression analysis. Apart from the proposed model, the Structural equation modeling is framed to determine the organizational performance by having employee engagement as a mediating construct.

Hypothesis

H1 : Talent Acquisition and Onboarding is having an effect on the organizational performance

H2 : Talent Retention is having an effect on the organizational performance

H3 : Career Management is having an effect on the organizational performance

H4 : Talent Philosophy is having an effect on the organizational performance

H5 : Employee Engagement is having an effect on the organizational performance

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the predictors of organizational performance using multiple regression.
2. To find the inter relationship between the talent management constructs and the organizational performance using correlation coefficient.

TABLE 1 CALCULATION OF RELIABILITY AND DESCRIPTIVE STATICS

	No of items	Reliability	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Std. Error	Kurtosis	Std. Error
Talent Acquisition and On boarding (TA)	5	0.826	4.03	0.75	0.57	-0.66	0.19	0.12	0.37
Talent Retention (TR)	5	0.693	3.82	0.73	0.53	-0.05	0.19	-0.89	0.37
Career Management (CM)	3	0.637	3.92	0.72	0.52	-0.23	0.19	-0.73	0.37
Employee Engagement (EE)	4	0.721	3.90	0.76	0.58	-0.56	0.19	0.10	0.37
Talent Philosophy (TP)	3	0.664	3.77	0.79	0.63	-0.44	0.19	-0.10	0.37
Organizational Performance (OP)	4	0.833	3.61	0.92	0.86	-0.46	0.19	-0.35	0.37

The reliability value for the construct “Organizational Performance” shows 0.833, (Mean=3.61, S.D=0.92). The skewness and kurtosis values are -0.46 and -0.35 shows the normality of the primary dataset collected. “Talent Acquisition and on boarding” shows the reliability value of 0.826, (Mean=4.03, S.D=0.75). The construct “Employee Engagement” shows the reliability score of 0.721(Mean=3.90, S.D=0.76). “Talent Philosophy” shows the reliability score of 0.664(Mean=3.77, S.D=0.79). The construct “Career Management” shows the Cronbach alpha score of 0.637(Mean=3.92, S.D=0.72). “Talent Retention” shows the Cronbach alpha score of 0.639(Mean=3.82, S.D=0.73). All the constructs reported the skewness and kurtosis score which is nearer to zero shows the normal distribution of the dataset.

TABLE 2 DETERMINATION OF CORRELATON COEFFICIENT

	TA	TR	CM	EE	TP	OP
Talent Acquisition and Onboarding	1					
Talent Retention	.780**	1				
Career Management	.615**	.657**	1			
Employee Engagement	.640**	.628**	.686**	1		
Talent Philosophy	.499**	.533**	.560**	.733**	1	
Organizational Performance	.509**	.571**	.612**	.620**	.627**	1
HYPOTHESIS	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Talent Acquisition and on boarding and organizational performance were positively related, $r(171) = 0.509$, $p < .001$. Talent Retention and organizational performance were positively related, $r(171) = 0.571$, $p < .001$. Career Management and organizational performance were positively related, $r(171) = 0.612$, $p < .001$. Employee Engagement and organizational performance were positively related, $r(171) = 0.620$, $p < .001$. Talent Philosophy and organizational performance were positively related, $r(171) = 0.627$, $p < .001$. All the five hypothesis are accepted.

TABLE 3 PREDICTORS OF ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-0.364	0.313		-1.162	0.247
TALENT ACQUISITION AND ONBOARDING	-0.016	0.112	-0.013	-0.147	0.883
TALENT RETENTION	0.227	0.119	0.178	1.91	0.058
CAREER MANAGEMENT	0.315	0.104	0.246	3.032	0.003
EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT	0.143	0.116	0.117	1.229	0.221
TALENT PHILOSOPHY	0.367	0.094	0.314	3.92	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Organizational Performance = $-0.364 + \text{Career Management} * (0.315) + \text{Talent Philosophy} * (0.367)$

The construct “Career Management” shows a b value of 0.315 which is significant ($\beta = 0.246$, $p < .001$). The construct “Talent Philosophy” shows a b value of 0.367 which is significant ($\beta = 0.314$, $p < .001$). Career Management and Talent Philosophy are found to be the significant predictor of the organizational performance.

**FIGURE 1 STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING
DETERMINATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE MEDIATION
OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT**

TABLE 4 REGRESSION WEIGHT ESTIMATION

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
EE	<---	TA	.218	.072	3.047	0.002
EE	<---	TR	.039	.078	0.505	0.614
EE	<---	CM	.291	.065	4.490	0.000
EE	<---	TP	.433	.052	8.342	0.000
OP	<---	EE	.753	.073	10.367	0.000

The AMOS model fit index determines the strength of the model. The Goodness of Fit index (GFI) shows a value of 0.934 which is above 0.9. The comparative fit index (CFI) shows a value of 0.943 which is above 0.9. The relationship between the construct Employee Engagement and the Talent Acquisition shows a C.R score of 3.047 which is greater than 1.96 , $p < 0.001$. The relationship between the construct Employee Engagement and the Talent Retention shows a C.R score of 0.505 which is lesser than 1.96, p value is 0.614 which is greater than 0.005 which is not significant. The relationship between the construct Employee Engagement and Career Management shows a C.R score of 4.490 which is greater than 1.96, p value is < 0.001 . The relationship between the construct Employee Engagement and Talent Philosophy shows a C.R score of 8.372 which is greater than 1.96, p value is < 0.001 . The relationship between Organizational performance and the Employee Engagement shows a CR value of 10.367, p value is < 0.001

DISCUSSIONS

The Talent Management practices are having a relationship with the organizational performance (Čizmić&Ahmić, 2021). The implementation of the talent management practices shows sustainable organizational performance (Aina&Atan, 2020). Apart from the conventional talent management practices, organizational performance shall be attained using technology (i.e Talent metrics and analytics) (Sivathanu& Pillai, 2019). In the present study the researcher proposed the hypothesis to determine the organizational performance. The constructs” Career Management” and” Talent Philosophy”

were found to be significant predictor of the organizational performance. Apart from the hypothesis framed, the researcher proved the moderating role of "Employee Engagement" in attaining the output" Organizational performance. This was proved using structural equation modeling. These findings add value to the previous study (Devi, 2017) where employee engagement moderates the relationship between talent management and the organizational performance.

Talent Management practices include sourcing and attracting the best talents which will improve the performance of the organization in terms of revenue and operations. Now organizations are moving one step ahead by adopting technology in implementing the Talent Management practices. The good execution of talent management practices will lead to a higher performance. Talent Acquisition and on boarding shall be through campus recruitments were young minds shall be moulded through pre placement talks and through pre assessments. Industry oriented syllabus in the college level and bridging the industry-academia thorough conferences and other professional forums will lead to have a better talent acquisition. Experiences people shall be recruited through social media portals like linkedin by verifying their accomplishments and verifiable achievements.

CONCLUSION

As per this study, talent philosophy should be very strong for an organization for an employer branding and sustainable organizational performance. The employee engagement practices shall be improvised in the organizations as it mediates the TM and the organizational performance. The firm outcome is effected by the talent management practices which includes organizational innovation and the employee turnover. (Son et al., 2020). In both the regression and the structural equation modeling, it shows "Career Management" is very important which is very clear that people work not only for the salary but for their progression. The employees shall be given an opportunity to study executive MBA or analytics course in the premier institutions and in top b schools through weekend mode for enhancing their knowledge and to improvise their leadership skills. Continuous learning and development will increase the employee engagement and the organizational performance.

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